

Deliverable D7

Report about a feasibility study to detect premature accelerated aging of Li-ion cells based on impedance measurements

EMPIR Grant Agreement number:

17IND10

Project short name:

LiBforSecUse

Lead partner

PTB

Partners:

KIT, PTB

Original due date: August 2020 (M24)

Revised due date: Feb 2022 (M42)

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 25 February 2022 (M42)

Feasibility study on accelerated aging detection in Li-ion cells based on impedance measurement

Deliverable D7 of the EMPIR – Project 17IND10 “LiBforSecUse”

This document specifies the feasibility of different impedance methods on the accelerated aging detection in Li-ion cell. The text on the following 12 pages forms deliverable D7.

1 Background

Accelerated aging is defined as the nonlinear decrease in the State of Health (SOH) of Li-ion cell. This nonlinear SOH decrease is usually apparent at the lower SOH range. Hence, this aging behaviour is detrimental and should be identified as early as possible.

For this purpose, the feasibility of different impedance based as well as nonlinear analysis methods to detect the risk of accelerated aging was evaluated. These methods should provide additional insight into cell internal processes as compared to the conventional capacity measurement. Hence, this may enable an indication of the onset of accelerated aging, which might not be possible by using conventional methods.

First, the data provided by the various analysis methods will be analysed to identify parameters that show characteristic changes arising primarily to the onset of accelerated aging. Then the identified parameters will be used to establish qualitative sudden death indicators, which should indicate, in the best case, the residual lifetime, but should at least qualitatively estimate the risk of accelerated aging. Finally, the significance of sudden death indicators will be compared for the various methods.

2 Data Set

The data set from the interlab comparison experiments (see D3 - LCT 1.1) was chosen for the feasibility study of the accelerated aging. There were in total 15 cells, which were cycled at 4 A from State of Charge (SOC) 0 % - 100 % under 45 °C at different partner institutions. Figure 1 shows the SOH decrease across the number of cycles. A slight deviation in the SOH decrease can be observed between different institutions, e.g., the cells at PTB were less aged while the cells at NPL were more significantly aged as compared to others. However, all cells generally follow almost similar aging trend and accelerated aging begins particularly when SOH exceeds under 70 - 80 % or after around 2000 cycles.

Figure 1: SOH decrease across the cycle number for (a) all the cells tested under LCT 1.1 and (b) specifically cells at KIT

Of all 15 cells, the KIT-06 and KIT-07 were explicitly selected for the upcoming feasibility evaluation of the accelerated aging. This is because additional Nonlinear Frequency Response (NFR) measurements are available for these cells and hence the significance of the evaluation of the various impedance-based analysis methods can be compared.

In a third approach impedance results from a larger number of life cycle tests were analysed by means of the Distribution of relaxation times (DRT) method. The goal of this approach is to outline a possible strategy for building a regression model to predict accelerated aging based on impedance data. For this purpose, the aging curves of six different cells measured at three institutions were investigated in more detail. The SOH of the respective cells is plotted as function of cycle number in Figure 2(a). As described above, two sections can be identified in the plots: a range at lower cycle numbers in which the decline in SOH proceeds at a constant rate and a range at higher cycle numbers in which the decline of the SOH accelerates. This general trend is found for all cells. However, the cycle number for which the transition from the constant aging phase to the accelerated aging phase occurs varies for the cells. Moreover, the aging rates, that is, the slope, differ in the two phases

Figure 2: (a) SOH of six different cells as function of cycle number and (b) the first derivative of the SOH against the cycle number. The horizontal line in (b) highlights the threshold above which the stage of accelerated aging is assumed to begin. The cycle numbers at which the respective cells exceed this limit are marked with a dot in (a) for each cell.

To describe how the aging behaviour changes over the course of the LCT, the first derivative of the SOH was formed. It is plotted in part (b) of the figure as the change of the SOH per 100 cycles as a function of cycle number. It basically replicates the findings of Figure (a): for lower cycle numbers (~500 to 2000 - 3000), cells age at a constant rate of about 1 SOH % per 100 cycles. For higher cycle number (above 2000 – 3000) the aging rate increases. Nevertheless, individual differences in the aging (such as the beginning of accelerated aging phase, the highest aging rate, etc.) of the different cells are more clearly highlighted in this plot. Besides these differences, however, the plot shows another common feature of the different cells: as soon as the aging rate becomes higher than $\sim 1.25 \text{ SOH} \% / 100 \text{ cycles}$ (highlighted by horizontal line in Figure 2(b)), all cells enter the phase of accelerated aging. Besides these differences, however, the plot shows another common feature of the different cells: as soon as the aging rate becomes higher than $\sim 1.25 \text{ SOH} \% / 100 \text{ cycles}$, all cells enter the phase of accelerated aging. In the following considerations, this rate is assumed to be the threshold value above which cells are in the phase of accelerated aging. In Figure 2(a), the cycle numbers at which the respective cell exceeds this threshold are highlighted. This illustrates that the SOHs at which the individual cells enter the accelerated aging phase vary significantly.

Since the capacity of the cells decreases two to three times faster in the case of accelerated aging, it is of great importance for the assessment of the suitability of cells for a second use not only to know its SOH, but also to have information on whether this phase has already started. Therefore, EIS parameters derived from the spectra by DRT are examined in section 3.3 for their correlation with the aging rate. Based on suitable predictors, a regression model is then established that allows an estimation of whether a cell is already in the stage of accelerated aging.

3 Results

3.1 Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

Figure 3 shows the typical aging behavior for KIT-06. From the impedance spectra, it is noticeable that the cell impedance is the largest at SOC 100 % and the smallest at SOC 20 %. During the life cycling test (LCT), the impedances at all selected SOCs increase predominantly in the second semicircle arc at the lower frequency range. In addition, the whole impedance spectra shift towards larger real impedance (Z'). The impedance increase in the second semicircle at lower frequency range could be associated with the charge transfer process at the electrode/electrolyte interface. Meanwhile, the spectrum shift could be due to the decrease in ionic conductivities of the electrolyte or an increase in the contact resistance, e.g., between the electrode particle or with current collectors. Similar aging behavior is also observed for KIT-07 as shown in Figure 4. However, both impedance spectra of KIT-06 and KIT-07 do not show any distinguishable feature that is relatable to the occurrence of the accelerated aging at around 2000th cycle as indicate in Figure 1(b).

For a closer investigation on the impedance development during LCT, impedances at SOC 100 % and at selected frequency points, i.e., 0.01 Hz, 0.1 Hz, 1 Hz, 10 Hz, 100 Hz and 1000 Hz, were plotted against the cycle number as shown in Figure 5. It can be seen that the impedance components, e.g., the real (Z') and imaginary parts (Z'') of the impedance as well as the magnitude of total impedance ($|Z|$) at lower frequency range (< 1 Hz) show constant increase over the cycles. Meanwhile, the impedances at frequencies range (> 1 Hz) show a distinctive inflection point at 2000th cycle (see insets in Figure 5), where the accelerated aging is taking place. Furthermore, the phase shift at 1 Hz also manifests similar distinctive inflection point that hints the onset of accelerated aging. These distinctive features observed in the development of different impedance components can be then served as the potential accelerated aging indicator.

The potential indicator for accelerated aging, e.g., the magnitude of the total impedance ($|Z|$) at SOC 100 % and 1000 Hz, can also be well correlated in other cells, which also show accelerated aging behavior. As shown in Figure 6, the potential indicator for accelerator aging suggests that KIT-07 and JRC-05 experience accelerated aging at about 2000th cycle while JRC-06 at about 3000th cycle. This can be well correlated to the sudden nonlinear SOH decrease as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 3: EIS during LCT for KIT-06 at different SOC. EIS were recorded with 0.5 A, under 23°C and from $10^2 - 10^4$ Hz.

Figure 4: EIS during LCT for KIT-07 at different SOC. EIS were recorded with 0.5 A, under 23°C and from 10^{-2} – 10^4 Hz.

Figure 5: The development of (a) Z' , (b) Z'' , (c) $|Z|$ and (d) phase shift during aging for KIT-06 at selected frequency points. Insets show the development of the respective impedance components at frequency points except at 0.01 Hz and 0.1 Hz. The impedance values are all taken from SOC 100 %

Figure 6: $|Z|$ at SOC 100 % and 1000 Hz for cells at both institution (a) KIT and (b) JRC show characteristic inflection point upon the onset of accelerated aging, i.e., 2000th cycle for KIT-07 and cell JRC-05 as well as 3000th cycle for JRC-06.

3.2 Nonlinear Frequency Response Analysis (NFRA)

Figure 7 shows second (Y_2) and third (Y_3) harmonic signals for KIT-06 during LCT. Both Y_2 and Y_3 mainly increase in the frequency region below 2 Hz during LCT and the harmonic signals are the most obvious at higher SOC range. The steady increase in the harmonic signals in the lower frequency range can be well correlated to the growth of second semicircle arc in the EIS, which is subjected to the charge transfer process at the electrode/electrolyte interface. This suggests that the charge transfer process is nonlinear in nature and this process is significantly hampered as the impedance as well as the corresponding nonlinearities increase during LCT. The similar behavior can also be observed for KIT-07 as shown in Figure 8. In general, no distinctive feature can be detected in both NFR-spectra that indicates the accelerated aging.

Meanwhile, by comparing the Y_3 to Y_2 signals at SOC 80 % and 0.1 Hz, two distinctive turning points can be observed as indicated in Figure 9. These turning points indicate that the switching of the contribution between Y_2 and Y_3 . When Y_3/Y_2 increases, this signifies that the contribution of Y_3 surpasses Y_2 , which means that the reaction rate of the charge transfer processes is predominantly impeded [1] [2] [3] and causes Y_3 to increase more than Y_2 . This can be then correlated to the linear SOH degradation in the second region stage of cell aging as shown in Figure 9(a). When Y_3/Y_2 decreases, this indicates that the contribution of Y_2 surpasses Y_3 , which means that the charge transfer process becomes more asymmetrical or the increase diffusive resistivity due to the porosity decrease in the electrode [1] [2] [3] and thus causes Y_2 to increase more than Y_3 . This can be correlated to the nonlinear SOH degradation not only in the third stage but also the first stage of cell aging as shown in Figure 9(a). Therefore, the turning point as observed in the Y_3/Y_2 has a potential to be further developed as an indicator for detecting the onset of accelerated aging.

Figure 7: NFR-spectra during LCT for KIT-06 at different SOC. NFR spectra were recorded with 5 A, under 23°C and from 10^{-1} – 10^2 Hz

Figure 8: NFR-spectra during LCT for KIT-07 at different SOC. NFR spectra were recorded with 5 A, under 23°C and from 10^{-1} – 10^2 Hz

Figure 9: (a) The three aging stages of KIT-06 and KIT-07 can be well correlated to (b) the distinctive turning points in Y_3/Y_2 at SOC 80 % and 0.1 Hz.

3.3 Distribution of relaxation times (DRT)

To identify suitable predictors for an aging rate prediction model, impedance spectra are analyzed by DRT. A typical DRT plot of an impedance spectrum of an 18650 cell is shown in Figure 10. The DRT has five different time constants from which the underlying resistance R and the corresponding capacitance C can be calculated.

Figure 10: plot of a DRT of an impedance spectrum an 18650 cell.

For impedance parameters to be suitable as predictors for the accelerated aging model, they must show a strong correlation with the aging rate. This means that such parameters must assume as constant values as possible in the range of low cycle numbers and increasing or decreasing values in the range of high cycle numbers. From the SOH estimation studies previously performed in the project, it is known that especially the impedance parameters in the range of low time constants - that is, at high frequencies - exhibit the dependence on the number of cycles described above. Moreover, this range was previously identified as suitable using the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (Section 3.1). In the following figure, the parameters R_1 , C_1 , R_2 , C_2 derived from the DRT plots are plotted against the cycle number.

Figure 11: plot of the impedance parameters R_1 , R_2 , C_1 and C_2 as a function of cycle number

The two parameters R_1 and R_2 fulfill the criterion of having constant values in the first phase of aging and increasing values in the second phase. For the respective cells, the plots differ mainly with respect to the cycle number at which the transition from constant to increasing values occurs. Consequently, the parameters R_1 and R_2 are considered as predictors. The curves of the two parameters C_1 and C_2 , on the other hand, do not correlate in the desired way and are not considered further. In the next step, the two parameters R_1 and R_2 are plotted directly against the aging rate (Figure 12).

Figure 12 resistances R_1 and R_2 as function of the aging rate

The plot of the resistance R_1 shows clear correlations for the individual cells with the aging rate - these cannot be found for the parameter R_2 . However, the plot of the parameter R_1 also shows, that the cells are shifted horizontally. To fully describe the relation between R_1 and the aging rate an additional weighting parameter is required. Since the different cells reach a certain aging rate at different SOHs, it is evident to take this influence into account for the modeling. Consequently, the parameters R_1 and the SOH are selected as predictors for the regression model.

For the estimation of the aging rate, a linear regression model was created using the Matlab tool *stepwiselm*. For parameterization and subsequent validation, the data shown above was randomly divided into four data sets, each with 75% training data and 25% test data, so that four-fold cross-validation could be performed. The results of all four runs of the cross-validation are shown in Figure 13. Therein, the estimated aging rates are plotted against the actual aging rates of the cells.

Figure 13: plot of the predicted ageing rate against the measured aging rate. The green boxes highlight areas in which the prediction is qualitatively correct. Areas of wrong predictions are highlighted with red boxes

The strong deviations of the points in Figure 13 from the horizontal show that the quantitative estimation of the aging rate is only of low precision. The qualitative information, namely whether there is an aging rate above the threshold or not, on the other hand, is estimated relatively well. In the figure, for all points lying within the green highlighted areas, the estimation is correct. Except for one cell (Inst. 1 cell 2 - red dots), only a very small number of estimates are incorrect (see red highlighted areas in the plot). The established model is thus able to make a statement about whether a cell is already in the stage of accelerated aging or not.

4 Conclusion

As conclusion, linear and nonlinear analysis methods are shown to be feasible to detect premature accelerated aging for Li-ion cells. In EIS, it is shown that impedance at higher frequency, e.g., at 1000 Hz, shows a distinct inflection point that indicates the onset of accelerated aging. Upon this inflection point, significant increase in the impedance at this specific frequency point can be observed. This could be possibly related to the increase in ohmic resistance either due to the contact resistance between electrode particles and electrode particle/current collector or the decrease in ionic conductivity of SEI and electrolyte.

Comparable correlations were also found in the study of the relationship of the aging rate with EIS parameters derived from the spectra using DRT. As in the direct impedance method approach, impedance parameters from the high-frequency region of the spectrum were identified as the most appropriate predictors of accelerated aging. These parameters are attributed in the literature to the contacting of the active material on the arrester of the electrodes. Consequently, it can be assumed that delamination of active material is one of the causes of accelerated aging. A first approach with a regression model could show that it is possible to derive a statement from impedance data whether a cell is already in the stage of accelerated aging. However, the wide variety of aging characteristics shown in Figure 2(b) suggests that a broader data basis is required for a general model.

Meanwhile, the nonlinear method, NFRA, also shows distinctive feature that well correlated to the different aging stages that are observed in the SOH degradation progression. The turning points, that signifies the switching of the contributions between Y_2 and Y_3 at lower frequency range, e.g., 0.1 Hz, has potential to be used as indicator to detect the accelerated aging in Li-ion cells. It is shown that when accelerated aging occurs, the contribution of Y_2 surpasses Y_3 . This can be related to the transition of the charge transfer process from symmetrical to asymmetrical behavior or the impedance increase of diffusion process due to the reduction in electrode porosity.

Based on the findings from both linear and nonlinear analysis methods, it is suggested that the accelerated aging in the Li-ion cells could be due to the following possible reasons:

- Increase in contact resistance between electrode particles or between electrode particle and current collector
- Decrease in ionic conductivity in SEI or electrolyte
- The transition of the charge transfer process from symmetrical to asymmetrical behavior
- The increase in impedance in the diffusion process possibly due to the decrease in electrode porosity.

5 References

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